

Mannich Reaction on Biphenols

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Mannich reaction on 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl with primary aromatic amines affords the oxaziny derivatives which on hydrolysis with ethanolic HCl furnish the aminomethyl derivatives, whereas secondary amines afford directly the aminomethyl derivatives.

Work of Burke and co-workers¹ in isolating the oxazino derivatives as the Mannich reaction products from phenols was a novelty of the Mannich reaction. As a part of our study on biphenols, it was thought of interest to study the Mannich reaction on biphenols.

4,4'-Dihydroxybiphenyl, when treated with excess of paraformaldehyde and 2.2 moles of benzylamine in ethanol at the room temperature, furnished a product which was found to be insoluble in NaOH and very sparingly soluble in HCl. Its analysis agreed with two bibenzoxaziny derivatives. On refluxing with EtOH-HCl it provided formaldehyde, identified by its 2,4-DNP, and another product, highly soluble in NaOH and HCl, indicating that the NaOH-insoluble compound was bibenzoxaziny derivative. 3,3'-Dibenzyl-2,4, 2', 4'-tetrahydro-6,6'-bi-(1, 3, 1', 3'-benzoxaziny) (Ia) structure has therefore been assigned to the bibenzoxaziny derivative. The hydrolysed product therefore should be 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(benzylaminomethyl)biphenyl (IIa). On treatment with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(benzylaminomethyl)biphenyl afforded 4,4'-diacetoxy-3,3'-di-(acetoxymethyl)biphenyl. With one mole of benzylamine and excess of paraformaldehyde, only the bibenzoxaziny derivative was formed.

Similarly, when 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl was subjected to the Mannich reaction with 2.2 moles of aniline and excess of paraformaldehyde, it afforded 3,3'-diphenyl-2, 4, 2',4'-tetrahydro-6,6'-bi-(1, 3, 1', 3'-benzoxaziny) (Ib) which on hydrolysis with EtOH-HCl furnished formaldehyde and 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dianilinomethylbiphenyl (IIb). The latter on treatment with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate afforded 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(acetoxymethyl)biphenyl, described earlier.

Mannich reaction of 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl in ethanol with excess of paraformaldehyde and 2.2 moles of each of (a) dimethylamine, (b) piperidine, and (c) morpholine afforded 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(dimethylaminomethyl)- (IIc), 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dipiperidinomethyl- (IId), and 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(morpholinomethyl)-biphenyl (IIe) respectively, since all of them, when treated with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, afforded 4,4'-diacetoxy-3,3'-di-(acetoxymethyl)biphenyl, described earlier.

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- (a) : R = $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$.
 (b) : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$.

- (a) : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$.
 (b) : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$.
 (c) : R = $-(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}$.

Mannich reaction of 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl with one mole of each of (a) piperidine and (b) morpholine afforded 4,4'-dihydroxy-3-piperidinomethylbiphenyl and 4,4'-dihydroxy-3-morpholinomethylbiphenyl, respectively, which on further Mannich reaction with excess of the respective amine provided the 3, 3'-di-derivatives, already described above.

4,4'-Dimethoxybiphenyl did not undergo the Mannich reaction with any of the primary or secondary amines. 2,2'-Dihydroxybiphenyl on the Mannich reaction with the above mentioned primary or secondary amine afforded only an unworkable mass.

*EXPERIMENTAL

3, 3'-Dibenzyl-2,4,2', 4'-tetrahydro-6,6'-bi-(1,3, 1', 3'-benzoxazinyl) (Ia).—To a mixture of paraformaldehyde (0.05M, 1.5g.) and benzylamine (0.03M, 3.2 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01M, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) was added and the reaction mixture kept overnight at the room temperature. The solvent was evaporated and the pasty product was dissolved in benzene and filtered. The solid obtained on removal of the solvent from the filtrate was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in white needles, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 80.3; H, 6.1; N, 6.2. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 80.4; H, 6.3; N, 6.3%).

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(benzylaminomethyl)biphenyl (IIa).—The preceding compound (1 g.) was slowly distilled with EtOH-HCl (10:5) on a wire gauze in a distilling flask and the distillate was collected in water. The distillation was continued till a solid began to separate in the distilling flask. The solution was just neutralised with sodium carbonate and the product separating was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 79.0; H, 6.8; N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 79.2; H, 6.6; N, 6.6%).

* All melting points are uncorrected.

The treatment of a portion of the distillate with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine afforded a yellow product, m.p. 166°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of the 2,4-DNP of formaldehyde was not depressed.

3,3'-Diphenyl-2,4,2',4'-tetrahydro-6,6'-bi-(1,3,1',3'-benzoxazinyI)(Ib).—To paraformaldehyde (0.03*M*, 0.9 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (5 ml), containing KOH (0.01 g.), aniline (2.2 ml) in the same solvent (5 ml) was added. To this mixture 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01*M*, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was left overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the product was worked up as usual. It was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture in white needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 79.6; H, 5.7; N, 6.5. $C_{26}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 5.7; N, 6.7%.)

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(phenylaminomethyl)biphenyl(IIb).—To the product (Ib) (1 g.) EtOH-HCl (15 ml, 2:1) was added; the mixture was slowly distilled and worked up as usual. The product (IIb) was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 78.5; H, 6.5; N, 7.0. $C_{26}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 78.8; H, 6.2; N, 7.1%.)

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(dimethylaminomethyl)biphenyl(IIc).—To paraformaldehyde (0.03*M*, 0.9 g.) dissolved in warm ethanol (10 ml), dimethylamine (3 ml, 37% aq. soln.) was added gradually with external cooling. 4,4'-Dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01*M*, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was then added and the mixture left overnight. The product separating was collected and crystallised from benzene in white cubes, m.p. 165°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 8.1; N, 9.4. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 8.0; N, 9.3%.)

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(piperidinomethyl)biphenyl(IIId).—4,4'-Dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01*M*, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to a mixture of paraformaldehyde (0.03*M*, 0.9 g.) and piperidine (0.025*M*, 2.2 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) and the mixture left overnight. The solvent was evaporated. It was worked up as usual and crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture, m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 75.9; H, 8.1; N, 7.4. $C_{24}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires C, 75.8; H, 8.4; N, 7.4%.)

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3-piperidinomethylbiphenyl.—To a solution of 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01*M*, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) a mixture of paraformaldehyde (0.01*M*, 0.9 g.) and piperidine (0.01*M*, 0.85 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was added and the mixture kept overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the product obtained was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 218°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 7.3; N, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 76.3; H, 7.4; N, 4.9%.)

The above piperidinomethylbiphenyl derivative was again treated with an excess of paraformaldehyde and piperidine in ethanol at the room temperature and worked up as usual to provide the biphenyl (IIId).

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(morpholinomethyl)biphenyl(IIe).—To a mixture of paraformaldehyde (0.03*M*, 0.9 g.) and morpholine (0.025*M*, 2.2 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) a solution of 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01*M*, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) was added and kept overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the product obtained was crystallised from benzene in white cubes, m.p. 187°. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 6.8; N, 7.5. $C_{28}H_{28}O_4N_2$ requires C, 68.8; H, 7.3; N, 7.3%.)

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3-morpholinomethylbiphenyl.—To a solution of 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (0.01 *M*, 1.85 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) a mixture of paraformaldehyde (0.01 *M*, 0.3 g.) and morpholine (0.01 *M*, 0.85 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was added dropwise and the mixture kept overnight. On working up as usual, it furnished crystals from benzene, m.p. 218°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 7.0; N, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N$ requires C, 71.7; H, 6.7; N, 4.9%.)

The above morpholinomethyl derivative on further Mannich reaction with excess of paraformaldehyde and morpholine furnished (IIe).

4,4'-Diacetoxy-3,3'-di-(acetoxyethyl)biphenyl.—4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-di-(aminomethyl)-biphenyl (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (10 ml) and fused sodium acetate (2 g.) for 1 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.5. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 63.8; H, 5.3%.)

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